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EUROPEAN UNION’S SPACE ACT’S “RIGHT OF WAY” RULES: DRIVING THE FUTURE OF ORBITAL TRAFFIC

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ABSTRACT

Article 103(3)(a)-(g) of the European Union’s proposed Space Act lists seven factors to determine which actor must move when avoiding a collision. Though Article 103(3) explicitly states that the list is non-exhaustive, the provision is otherwise silent regarding the interpretation of the factors. A sequential interpretation allows for each point to be considered in a simple method by starting with (a) and ending with (g). However, Article 103(3) is unclear whether it can or should be interpreted sequentially. This paper evaluates Article 103(3)(a)-(g) by combining textual analysis with technical considerations and using long-standing principles from aviation and maritime law. In finding Article 103(a)-(g) lacks practicality for sequential interpretation, this paper proposes a re-ordering of the factors (a)-(g). This new order of factors allows for sequential application when determining which actor has the right-of-way in a collision avoidance manoeuvre. Accompanying each of the seven factors is a rule statement for operators’ use during a potential collision.

The purpose of right-of-way rules is to provide space actors with predictability in their operations. Resolving conjunction events on an ad-hoc basis threatens operator efficiency and cannot be scaled to larger systems such as constellations. The EU Space Act tasks “Collision Avoidance Space Services Providers” with resolving operator disputes and deciding on a manoeuvre strategy when a collision is imminent. Given this time-sensitive mission, there must be a clear understanding of Article 103(3). Additionally, clarifying the language and application of Article 103(3) reinforces the EU’s sovereignty because comprehensible and effective regulations are more likely to become a global standard.

KEYWORDS: Right-of-way, Space Traffic Management, Orbital Rules, European Union Space Law, Collision Avoidance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The 2009 collision between the American satellite, Iridium-33, and the Russian satellite, Kosmos 2251, evidences the threat of orbital collisions, becoming a real concern among space actors.² In the worst-case scenario, a collision could obliterate a satellite, rendering it defunct and creating thousands, if not hundreds-of-thousands, of debris objects.³ In the best-case scenario, a satellite operator can proactively conduct a Collision Avoidance Manoeuvre (CAM)⁴ to reduce the risk of collision, but such manoeuvres interrupt satellite service and expend vital fuel reserves.⁵ This means that CAMs are an expensive endeavour, costing about 5-10% of total mission costs.⁶

In a potential collision, satellite operators must therefore decide between conducting a CAM or allowing their satellite to collide with another. Incentivized to preserve satellite operations and prevent a collision, the question for operators then becomes: *which* satellite should move?

Right-of-way (ROW) rules, or “rules of the road,” guide the decision of “who has the right to stay a course and who has the obligation to move out of the way to avoid a collision.”⁷ In the context of space activities, the operator with the ROW maintains course,⁸ and the operator conducting the CAM is “giving-way.”

Dictating who has the right to move in a collision path fits under a larger traffic management system, known as Space Traffic Management (STM). Though a definition has yet to be internationally recognized, nonetheless codified, the European Union has defined STM as: “an approach to safely and sustainability enter into, conduct activities in, and return from outer space.”⁹

² European Space Agency, (n.d.) *About space debris*, Space Safety, retrieved 5 October 2025, from https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/About_space_debris (Iridium-33 and Kosmos 2251 collided at a speed of 11.7km/s, destroying both satellites and creating more than 23,000 trackable debris fragments).

³ Foust, J., SpaceNews, *Potential Satellite Collision Shows Need for Active Debris Removal*, (January 29, 2020) (the conjunction of two upper stages at 981 kilometres would create between 3,375 and 12,860 objects at least 5 to 10 centimetres in size and more than 200,000 debris objects at least 1 centimetre in size).

⁴ “‘Collision avoidance’ means the execution of collision avoidance manoeuvres to reduce the risk of collision in outer space.” European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 5 point 36 at 42, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD).

⁵ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) at 138, COM(2025) 335 Final, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf.

⁶ OECD (2022), *Earth’s Orbits at Risk: The Economics of Space Sustainability*, at 31, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/16543990-en>.

⁷ Frandsen, H. O., (2023), *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 299, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>. See Chen, Y., Lai, Z., Li, H., et al., (2023, Oct. 2-6), *A Networking Perspective on Starlink’s Self-Driving LEO Mega-Constellation* [Conference Article], at 3, ACM MobiCom ’23: Proceedings of the 29th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking, Madrid, Spain, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3570361.3592519>, (Orbital manoeuvres “use the satellite’s propulsion system to raise/lower altitude, change speeds, or adjust its orbital inclination angles.”).

⁸ See *infra* note 52 (The terminology of “maintaining course” is intentional and reflects principles of maritime law.).

⁹ De Man, P., Doumbouya, L., Lacroix, L., et al. (2022), *Pilot Project on Space Traffic Management: The Rise of Importance of Space Traffic Management (STM) Final Report*, at 26, Publications Office of the European Union.

Currently, no ROW or STM framework exists.¹⁰ The issue is self-evident: without ROW rules, efficiency is hampered because actors must resolve each potential collision on a case-by-case basis. Best described by Hjalte Osborn Frandsen: “Imagine if every time you met another car at an intersection, you had to get out and coordinate with the other driver, about who should go first.”¹¹ The process is further complicated, considering that an operator must be able to correctly identify whose spacecraft is on the conjunction event before initiating contact.¹² Then, once the owner or operator of the spacecraft is identified, communication between the two typically uses ad hoc methods like e-mails or phone calls.¹³ In total, the lack of a ROW or STM framework translates into a multi-step problem demanding significant resources and time.

The European Union’s Space Act provides a solution in Article 103(3), which lists seven factors to be taken into consideration when determining which operator in a potential collision has the ROW:

- (a) Protection of Crew Vehicle;
- (b) Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation;
- (c) Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres
- (d) State of the Spacecraft;
- (e) Eccentricity of the Spacecraft’s Orbits;
- (f) Age of the Spacecraft; and
- (g) Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission.¹⁴

When there is a significant chance of collision between satellites, known as a High Interest Event (HIE),¹⁵ operators must discuss who should conduct the CAM.¹⁶ Typically, a significant chance of collision is denoted as a Probability of Collision (PoC) of $1E-4$.¹⁷ This means that if a satellite’s trajectory is within 1

¹⁰ Oltrogge, D. L., Christensen, I. A., (9–12 December 2019), *Space Governance in the New Space Era*, [First International Orbital Debris Conference] IOC 2019 Conference, Sugar Land, Texas, United States, <https://www.hou.usra.edu/meetings/orbitaldebris2019/orbital2019paper/pdf/6013.pdf>, 7.4 Space Governance Gap Analysis, Table 1, (“Rules-of-the-road” are a “gap” in space governance). See National Space Society, (6 May 2025), *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy,

https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf, at 1 (“[A]n international space traffic coordination system is elusive.”).

¹¹ Frandsen, 2023, at 302. Hjalte Osborn Frandsen is a PhD Fellow from the University of Copenhagen.

¹² European Commission, (15 February 2022), *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report) at 11, JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004>, (“[A]ll satellite operators providing services within the EU should register with a collision avoidance service . . . to ensure timely responses and coordinated collision avoidance manoeuvres.”).

¹³ See *infra* section 1.2 Lack of Governing Structure (To resolve a conjunction between the ESA’s Aerolius and SpaceX’s Starlink, the operators communicated via email).

¹⁴ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 103(3), at 105, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁵ HIE “means close approaches with a high level of risk, potentially requiring collision avoidance manoeuvres to be performed by a space operator.” European Commission (2025), Space Act, at 43.

¹⁶ European Commission, (2025), Space Act, at 43.

¹⁷ See Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G., (2023), *Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management*, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf. See also American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), (24 October 2022), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice C-2: Perform CA Risk Assessment to

kilometre (0.62 miles) of another, thus rendering a 1 in 10,000 chance of collision, operators must discuss CAMs to mitigate the likelihood of a collision.¹⁸

If a resolution between operators can't be made within a "reasonable time," the process turns over to a "Collision Avoidance Space Services Provider" (CASSP).¹⁹ The CASSP is tasked with proposing a strategy based on Article 103(3)(a)-(g), shown above.²⁰ The text of Article 103(3) clarifies that the CASSP's strategy is not limited to the provided seven elements, but at bottom, the CASSP must take all seven elements into account. In practice, this means Article 103(3) is not exhaustive, but the CASSP must base their strategy on the considerations provided in Article 103(3)(a)-(g). Throughout this paper, references to "operators" can include CASSPs, but references to "CASSPs" only address CASSPs.

1.1. Proliferation of Space Objects

As space activity increases, the risk of collision between spacecraft will undoubtedly follow.²¹ This is especially true in the context of constellations, where hundreds or thousands of spacecrafts are clustered together to form one "mega-constellation" or "giga-constellation."²² One of the more notable constellations, SpaceX's Starlink, conducted 144,404 CAMs between December 2024 and May 2025, averaging one manoeuvre every 1.8 minutes.²³ In a constellation, not only does the risk of collision exist with other orbiting objects, but collisions can occur within the constellation itself, known as an "intra-collision" risk. This dual risk is too much for an operator to manage, and thus, automated CAM systems are used.²⁴

With space operations increasing in frequency, European stakeholders are feeling the heat: 72.7% strongly agree that there is a "growing risk for collision stemming from an intensification of space activities."²⁵ With more actors in orbit, the probability of a collision between any two objects increases. For instance, a data model determined that each year, a satellite can expect over one-million potential encounters.²⁶ Of these one-million encounters, nearly 25,000 are considered HIE.²⁷

The population swell in Earth's orbit increases the frequency of conjunction alerts, making it difficult for operators to parse out real threats. As referenced above, the 2009 collision between Iridium-33 and

Identify High-Risk Conjunctions That Require Mitigation, at 12 (supporting the use of PoC of 1E-4 for baseline assessments and the use of 1E-05 for conservative assessments).

¹⁸ Szondy, D., (2025, August 26), *ESA Applies CREAM to Tackle Growing Space Debris Threat*, New Atlas, <https://newatlas.com/space/esa-cream-space-debris/>.

¹⁹ European Commission, (2025), Space Act, at 41, 105, (In the EU, the EU-Space Surveillance and Tracking (SST) Programme provides collision avoidance (CA) services.)

²⁰ European Commission, (2025), Space Act, Article 103(3), at 105.

²¹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (June 2023), *UNOOSA and ESA Release Updated Infographics About Space Debris*, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/informationfor/media/unoosa-and-esa-release-infographics-and-podcasts-about-space-debris.html>.

²² See European Commission, (2025), Space Act, Article V (Definitions).

²³ O'Callaghan, J., (1 October 2025) *Heavy Traffic Ahead*, Aerospace America, <https://aerospaceamerica.aiaa.org/features/heavy-traffic-ahead/#:~:text=Mega%20numbers,from%2012%2C000%20to%2042%2C000%20satellites>.

²⁴ See section 4.6 Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation.

²⁵ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Impact Assessment Report* (Annex Report 2) at 16, SWD(2025) 335 Final, Part 2/2.

²⁶ Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G., (2023), *Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management*, at 17, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf (Space population as of 2 April 2023 and detected at a significance of $P_c > 1E-7$).

²⁷ *Ibid.* (Space population as of 2 April 2023, plus 34,000 satellites to represent the expected population of SpaceX's Starlink and Amazon's Kupier satellites with a significance detection of $P_c > 1E-4$).

Cosmos 2251 decimated both spacecrafts.²⁸ The estimated PoC between the two satellites was around 3 in 100,000—about one-third of the HIE manoeuvre threshold (1 in 10,000).²⁹ Not only was the PoC not significant enough to warrant a CAM, but this was one of thirty-seven other conjunctions that week.³⁰ From the operators’ perspective, it was a needle in a haystack: “the conjunction which eventually led to an actual disastrous collision did not stand out of the lot.”³¹

It is impractical for operators to respond to every conjunction alert. Operators must focus on the potential collisions with the highest risk, and once identified, each CAM requires careful planning to implement. The last thing an operator needs is a “secondary conjunction,” which occurs when the original CAM puts the spacecraft back into harm’s way, this time with a higher risk of collision with a second object. For instance, if spacecraft B conducts a CAM to avoid collision with spacecraft A, a secondary conjunction would result in spacecraft B’s CAM creating another collision risk, but this time with spacecraft C.

Whether or not an automated CAM system is used to alleviate the operator’s burden, all CAMs reduce the lifetime of the hardware itself, because a satellite needs to expend extra fuel to conduct a manoeuvre. It follows that the more conjunction events that occur, the more CAMs a satellite needs to conduct, and the less life a system gets. Moreover, when conducting a CAM, the satellite turns its instruments off, causing an interruption in service or “missed science and data” collection.³² The cost of a CAM is comprised of the meticulous planning of operators, reduced lifetime of spacecraft, and interruption in service.

Given the price to conduct a CAM and the high frequency of conjunction events, spacecraft operators are incentivized to conduct CAMs only when there is a true emergency. In such a scenario, the countdown to collision will be quick, so operators must act fast.

1.2. *Lack of Governing Structure*

In 2019, the European Space Agency’s (ESA) Aeolus satellite had a 1 in 50,000 PoC with a Starlink satellite. As time continued, the PoC increased to 1 in 10,000. Reacting to the HIE alert, ESA operators reached SpaceX via email, but these communications were left unanswered.³³ Ultimately, Aeolus conducted a CAM and successfully prevented a collision between the two satellites.³⁴

The situation between Aeolus and Starlink illustrates the ad-hoc nature of collision-avoidance communications. There are no shared protocols for collision avoidance procedures, so each operator is forced to resolve conjunction events through phone calls or e-mails.³⁵ Although remedying a HIE is in both party’s interest, a spam filter on one’s phone could mean the difference between a successful CAM or a catastrophic collision.

Not only is the mode of communication subject to improvement, but without an instruction manual to guide the conversation, the discussions between operators across the world can vary in transparency and collaboration. Operators might be less willing to divulge information about their spacecraft, citing proprietary or national security concerns. And given the cost of conducting a CAM, operators might be less willing to offer to move.

²⁸ European Space Policy Institute, (January 2020), *ESPI Report 71 – Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management – Full Report*, at 26.

²⁹ *Ibid.*

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² *Ibid.*

³³ European Space Policy Institute, (January 2020), at 27, (“[A]fter the event became public, SpaceX blamed a bug in the company’s warning system, which prevented the operator from seeing the follow-on correspondence on this probability increase.”).

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297–318, at 299, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

When time is of the essence, operators are forced to evaluate a conjunction event based on their subjective analysis and employ negotiation tactics to determine who should have the ROW.³⁶ Far from efficient, the orbital terrain is likened to a present-day “Wild West”³⁷ where the incentivized behaviours are those in one’s self-interest.³⁸ In such a volatile environment, the predictability of operations is nearly non-existent.³⁹

1.3. *The Need for Right-of-Way (ROW) Rules*

ROW rules minimize the need for “individual and frequent negotiations,” allowing CASSPs to resolve conjunction events without engaging in operator-to-operator negotiations or contracting into bilateral agreements.⁴⁰ The less coordination required between actors equates to a lower transaction cost for participants.⁴¹ Therefore, a ROW framework “is essential for safe and economic operations in any traffic domain with many uncoordinated participants and no central actor coordinating the traffic.”⁴² By making behaviour predictable, the risk associated with space activities is reduced.⁴³

Given the time-sensitive nature of a HIE, “a standardised procedure on rules of the road should be established.”⁴⁴ ROW rules would alleviate the stress on operators during HIE alerts, enabling spacecraft operators to focus on the conjunction events that matter. “The requirement for a satellite to execute an avoidance manoeuvre resulting from a conjunction alert implies a regulatory mandate.”⁴⁵

³⁶ Frandsen, H. O., (2021, Oct. 25-29), *Agreeing on the Rules-of-the-Road* [Conference article], at 7, 72nd International Astronautical Congress, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3976854>.

³⁷ Vasile, M. & Wilson, A., (2023), The Space Sustainability Paradox, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 423, 138869, at 4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138869> (“[S]pace is becoming like the Wild West and no one can be held legally accountable for their actions.”).

³⁸ Frandsen, 2021, at 8 (“[I]ndividual actors will be incentivised to make [] bilateral arrangements to ensure the safe and efficient handling of conjunctions. Such agreements . . . will not necessarily improve the overall sustainability and safety for the orbital domain.”).

³⁹ For States, this causes an additional issue. See *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty) art. VI, VII, 19 December 1966, 610 U.N.T.S. 205 (States are internationally liable for damage to another State Party caused by domestic, non-government space activities.); *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects* (Liability Convention) art. III, 29 March 1972, 961 U.N.T.S. 187 (Liability for collisions in orbit are apportioned according to fault).

⁴⁰ See *supra* note 38. See also European Commission, (2025), Space Act, Article 103(1)(c), at 105, (Bilateral agreements between operators can contractually designate which spacecraft will have the ROW. In enforcing contractual obligations, the risk cannot be externalized to third parties through no secondary conjunctions.); see also American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), (24 October 2022), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice C-3: Pursue Adequate Mitigation Actions to Avoid High-Risk Conjunctions, at 13, (“Ensure that the selected mitigation action does not create any additional conjunctions that both exceed the high-risk threshold and that cannot subsequently be mitigated”).

⁴¹ Frandsen, H., (2021, Oct. 25-29), *Agreeing on the Rules-of-the-Road* [Conference article], at 2, 72nd International Astronautical Congress, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3976854> (Transaction costs are lowered “for participants in a system by eliminating or reducing the need for frequent coordination between actors.”)

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ Council of the European Union, (5 December 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience, and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union (EU Space Act)* (Annex), 2025/0335 (COD), 16437/25, Point (62c) at 21.

⁴⁵ Stilwell, R. E., (16 January 2018), *UTM, ATM, STM . . . slices of the sky?* [Conference Presentation], Section 2.3.4. Barriers, Space Traffic Management Conference, 2018 Seeking Sustainable Solutions, Daytona Beach, Florida, United States, <https://commons.erau.edu/stm/2018/presentations/5>.

2. ARTICLE 103(3) ANALYSIS: EVALUATION OF AN IMPLICIT HIERARCHY

Although the text of Article 103(3) specifies that the factors are not exhaustive, the text is silent regarding their exact interpretation. A natural assumption is to apply the factors sequentially by considering each point one-by-one, starting with (a) and ending with (g). Sequential interpretation is likely preferred because of its common-sense use, simple structure, and ease in application, but it is unclear whether Article 103(3) can or should be interpreted sequentially.

Determining whether Article 103(3) can or should be applied sequentially is especially necessary because failing to adhere to Article 103(3) is a breach of a CASSPs obligation.⁴⁶ If a CASSP fails to apply Article 103(3) properly, they will be subject to liability.⁴⁷ The EU's laudable effort in creating a ROW framework is eclipsed by uncertainty: is there a sequential hierarchy in Article 103(3)?

2.1. Textual Interpretation

The Article 103(3) factors are examined in light of the surrounding text, technical considerations, and principles in maritime and aviation law.⁴⁸ The advantage of this approach is its inclusion of equitable considerations, like fairness, which have permeated maritime and aviation law but otherwise might be overshadowed by a strict technical approach. The drawback of this approach is that it can lead to unwarranted conclusions, since the factors are not expressly defined.

The primary obstacle in evaluating the Article 103(3) factors is the lack of a clear definition. Although the interpretation of factor (a), “*the protection of a crewed vehicle*,” is straightforward, other factors fail to define key terms. The lack of textual clarity makes it difficult to maintain the intention of the original drafters.⁴⁹

It is helpful to analogize to maritime and aviation law for the formulation of ROW rules because these domains have successfully utilized rule-based approaches in traffic management.⁵⁰ The respective

⁴⁶ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex X, Point 5.2, at 35, COM(2025) 335 Final, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf (“A collision avoidance space service provider infringes . . . Article 103(3), first subparagraph, by failing to base the strategy of action on the principles laid down in the first subparagraph.”)

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ Bertrand, R., Michel, M., (20–23 April 2021), *Assessment of Inter-Operator Rule-Based Collision Avoidance Operations* [Conference Presentation], Section 5: Conclusions and Future Work, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/> (“Rule-based approaches have the potential to be a feasible solution to determine what operator has to initiate an avoidance manoeuvre in case of a potential collision between two manoeuvrable satellites”).

⁴⁹ Without supplemental explanation, the interpretation of Article 103(3) varies. Subjective interpretation makes it difficult to understand exactly what circumstances the Article 103(3)(a)-(g) factors are intended to alleviate or circumvent. Thus, it is difficult to construct a ROW rule that maintains the intention of the original drafters. For example, in Article 103(3)(g) “Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission,” a rule for a “payload launch” would be: *In case of conjunction, the spacecraft launching with a payload must give-way to in-orbit spacecraft*. An example for a “navigation satellite” would be: *In case of conjunction, the spacecraft providing navigation service is responsible for staying on course unless the other spacecraft is providing communication services*. Both “payload launch” and “navigation satellite” address the phase and the type of the mission, but by changing the interpretation of Article 103(3)(g), it alters the ROW rule. Both ROW rules stated here stem from the text of Article 103(3)(g), yet they are completely different: one describes the ROW for launching payloads, the other describes in-orbit spacecraft providing services. The risk of interpreting Article 103(3) is the potential for error.

⁵⁰ See *supra* note 48 (“Potential technological barriers to implementation [of rule-based approaches to traffic management] are low, and the approach is known and proven in other traffic domains.”). See also Ligor, D. C., McClintock, B., McCormick, D., (25 June 2023), Rand Corporation, *Cross-Domain Lessons for Space Traffic Management: An Analysis of Air and Maritime Treaty Governance Mechanisms*, Research Report, “Key Findings,”

maritime and aviation industry “flourished by virtue of stable, internationally accepted rules, which regulate navigation.”⁵¹ The same can be accomplished in the space industry.

In summary, the following trifecta is utilized in the evaluation of Article 103(3)(a)–(g): (1) textual interpretation; (2) technical considerations; and (3) maritime and aviation law.⁵²

2.2. Maritime Background

Promulgated by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), the *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea* (1994) (UNCLOS) sets forth binding international maritime law.⁵³ The *International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea* (1972) (COLREG) provide the “rules of the road” for maritime navigation. Both are widely known instruments in the context of maritime law, making it a useful comparison to space law.⁵⁴ Space lawyers can essentially “adopt” legal principles that have “proved beneficial to commerce on the oceans” for use and application in space law.⁵⁵ For space regulations to be as long-lasting and globally appreciated as UNCLOS, “space lawyers need some appreciation of maritime law.”⁵⁶

Maritime law designates ships as either give-way vessels or stand-on, each attributed with respective obligations when avoiding a collision.⁵⁷ “Give-way vessels have the obligation to manoeuvre and stay out of the way. Stand-on vessels have the obligation to maintain course and speed and only manoeuvre if needed to avoid collision.”⁵⁸

Space and maritime law have similarities and differences. As to the former, the space and maritime industry mirror each other in the rising demand for traffic system stability.⁵⁹ Like the revolutionary advancement of cargo ships, features like New Space⁶⁰ and reusable rocket systems are driving the demand for STM.⁶¹ There are important distinctions between the two domains. Maritime law originated between 900 and 300 BCE, evolving at common law for hundreds of years, whereas space law is new and

www.rand.org/t/RRA2208-2, (“Elements of the ICAO [International Civil Aviation Organization] and IMO [International Maritime Organization] governance frameworks may serve as analogues for the creation of an international space traffic management organization”).

⁵¹ DeSaussure, H. (1981). Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts (An Oceanic View of Space Transport), *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 94.

⁵² Ultimately, the advantage of this trifecta approach outweighs the disadvantage because it is flexible and equitable for considerations that are outside the scope of this paper but nonetheless might be important (such as determining what behaviours to incentivize).

⁵³ See *infra* note 85. The binding nature of UNCLOS comes from its status as customary international law (CIL). Once CIL, obligations are binding on all states, regardless of ratification status.

⁵⁴ DeSaussure, H., (1981), Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts (An Oceanic View of Space Transport), *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 103, (“[Space lawyers] need to become conversant with basic admiralty rules . . . It is with this perspective that they can compare the two environments”).

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ Frandsen, H. O., (2023), Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol. 48(3), 297–318, at 306, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> (“The requirement for stand-on vessels to refrain from manoeuvring is there to maximize predictability for the manoeuvring vessel.” The use of obligations, rather than rights, in right-of-way rules is adopted from COLREGS).

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ DeSaussure, H. (1981). Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts (An Oceanic View of Space Transport), *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 93.

⁶⁰ European Commission, (10 March 2023), *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence* at 4 footnote 11, JOIN(2023) 9 final, Brussels, Belgium, (“New Space” refers to the economic change regarding space initiatives, specifically the low cost and high return relationship, encouraging involvement and resulting in significantly more space actors).

⁶¹ DeSaussure, H. (1981). Maritime and Space Law Comparisons and Contrasts: An Oceanic View of Space Transport, *Journal of Space Law*, vol. 9, no. 1 & 2, 93–104, at 93.

thus lacks comparable precedent.⁶² Additionally, a vessel operating in the sea makes two-dimensional manoeuvres, but spacecraft in Earth’s orbit makes three-dimensional manoeuvres. Not only are the dimensions different, but operating a spacecraft in orbit is counterintuitive; to move a spacecraft into a higher orbit, an operator must slow the velocity of the spacecraft and vice versa.

Other objects in space are tracked and reported in Space Situational Awareness (SSA) data.⁶³ Because operators are unable to visually determine if they are on a conjunction path, they must rely on SSA capabilities to inform them of their surroundings. On the seas, however, COLREGS Rule 5 mandates that “[e]very vessel shall at all times maintain a proper look-out by sight and hearing . . . so as to make a full appraisal of the situation and of the risk of collision.”⁶⁴ The comparison between situational input mechanisms—SSA data or visual sight—underscores the importance of accurate SSA data for spacecraft operators.

The domains of space and maritime traffic management are nevertheless entwined: “[I]n the case of re-entry, the space object might end up in the sea, carrying implications for sea traffic management.”⁶⁵

2.3. Aviation Background

The interconnectedness of Aviation Traffic Management (ATM) and STM is already recognized within the EU.⁶⁶ Given the proximity of airspace and space, developing an STM approach “cannot be in complete isolation from existing conventions at the airspace level.”⁶⁷ The origin of aviation law occurred at the *Convention on International Civil Aviation* (1948) (Chicago Convention) with the creation of the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). The Chicago Convention is not customary international law (CIL),⁶⁸ but the domestic principles are largely based on the Chicago Convention.⁶⁹ Notably, Annex 2 in the Chicago Convention contains the ROW rules, which are regarded as mandatory because “safe and efficient air travel requires internationally uniform traffic rules.”⁷⁰

⁶² & Bedigian, LLC, *History of Maritime Law*, accessed September 23, 2025 (<https://www.gilmanbedigian.com/history-of-maritime-law>). See Vasile, M. & Wilson, A., (2023), The Space Sustainability Paradox, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 423, 138869, at 4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138869> (“[T]he legal systems we have in place regarding space are nowhere near as comprehensive as in other spheres such as maritime law”).

⁶³ SpaceWays (May 2022). *First STM Brief: A Congested Space and its Safety*, at 3 (Space Situational Awareness (SSA) is defined as, “A holistic approach, including comprehensive knowledge and understanding of the main space hazards, encompassing collision between space objects, fragmentation, and re-entry of space objects into the atmosphere, space weather events, and near-Earth objects”).

⁶⁴ International Maritime Organization (1972). *Convention on the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea*, (COLREG) (1972), Rule 5. See Baldauf, M., Benedict, K., Fischer, S., Motz, F., & Schröder-Hinrichs, J-U., (11 April 2011), Collision Avoidance Systems in Air and Maritime Traffic, *Journal of Risk and Reliability*, vol. 225, doi: 10.1177/1748006X11408973, 333–343, at 334, (23% of maritime collisions are caused by poor look-out).

⁶⁵ De Man, P., Doumbouya, L., Lacroix, L., et al. (2022). *Pilot Project on Space Traffic Management: The Rise of Importance of Space Traffic Management (STM) Final Report*, at 236, Publications Office of the European Union.

⁶⁶ European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), at 3, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (Regulation (EU) 376/2014 sets forth a mandatory reporting scheme for incidents at the intersection between aviation and space activities.).

⁶⁷ De Man, P., Doumbouya, L., Lacroix, L., et al. (2022), at 236.

⁶⁸ See *supra* note 53; see also *infra* note 85.

⁶⁹ Article I of the Chicago Convention reaffirms the following principle: “every State has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory.”

⁷⁰ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 308, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

The Chicago Convention, like COLREGS, outlines ROW rules for aircraft. Chapter 3.2.2 starts the “right-of-way” regulations and states: “The aircraft that has the right-of-way shall maintain its heading and speed.”⁷¹ When two aircraft are heading directly towards each other, both aircrafts must manoeuvre to the right to avoid a collision.⁷² An exception to this rule is provided in Chapter 3.2.2.3 with a “pecking order” that stimulates what kind of aircraft must give way. As one example: “power-driven aircraft shall give way to aircraft which are seen to be towing other aircraft or objects.”⁷³ Also, when approaching to land, aircraft must give-way to those at lower altitudes.⁷⁴

2.4. ROW Rule Statement and Decision Matrix

Herein, the Article 103(3) factors are presented with a ROW rule statement, designating which spacecraft has the ROW and which must give way. The rules are then combined to form the Decision Matrix, a visual guide to understanding how the rule statements work together.⁷⁵ When proposing CAMs, the CASSP should refer to the Decision Matrix to decide who receives the ROW.

The operators themselves can use the ROW rules, before CASSP involvement is necessary. As a reminder, CASSP involvement is triggered when operators are unable to find a solution in a “reasonable time.”⁷⁶ It’s worth mentioning, however, that some spacecraft data is argued to be proprietary, and therefore, it won’t be available to other operators. In such a situation, CASSP involvement might be necessary.

CASSPs are third-party neutrals who can rectify disagreements between operators. But once a situation demands CASSP involvement, a CASSP will be under immense time pressure to render a strategy decision. Time cannot be spent interpreting Article 103(3). This paper provides rules for each factor under Article 103(3). Assuming textual interpretation and technical considerations are correct, these rules should properly embody the Article 103(3) elements and their application to the ROW analysis.

2.5. Limitations on Article 103(3)

The Space Act imposes several key restraints on Article 103, which are adopted as general parameters in this paper. The first limitation is in Article 103(1), which specifies that the Article only applies to HIEs between two manoeuvrable spacecraft.⁷⁷ This limitation effectively omits objects like space debris from the discussion, since they completely lack manoeuvrability capacity.⁷⁸ Second, Article 2 states that the Space Act does not apply to military spacecrafts.⁷⁹ Third, per Point 5.2 Title X in the Annex, proposed CAMs must comply with the following principles:

- (a) Take the utmost account of the protection of crewed vehicles;⁸⁰
- (b) Reduce the initial collision risk by at least one order of magnitude below the manoeuvre threshold for High Interest Event Alert; and
- (c) Not create unreasonable risks of secondary conjunctions.⁸¹

Point (a) mirrors Article 103(3)(a) in its recognition of crewed vehicles. This is further evaluated in Section 2.1 Crewed Vehicles, presented below. Point (b) regards itself with the outcome of the CAM by

⁷¹ Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.

⁷² Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.2.

⁷³ Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.3(d).

⁷⁴ Chicago Convention, Annex 2, Ch. 3.2.2.5.2.

⁷⁵ The Decision Matrix is presented in Section 5 Right-of-Way (ROW) Decision Matrix.

⁷⁶ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article 103(3), at 105.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Where relevant, considerations of non-maneuvrable spacecraft are briefly addressed. See section 4.5 Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres.

⁷⁹ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article 2(3)(a)&(b), at 38.

⁸⁰ See section 4.1 Protection of Crew Vehicle.

⁸¹ See *supra* note 40.

providing that the Probability of Collision (PoC) should be reduced by “at least one order of magnitude” below the alert threshold.⁸² The complexities of point (b) lie outside the scope of this paper, but it is important to note that operators and CASSPs are held to this standard. Finally, point (c) requires operators and CASSPs to consider secondary conjunctions, as described in section 1.1 *Proliferation of Space Objects*. As a reminder, a secondary conjunction arises from a spacecraft’s CAM by creating another conjunction event with a second spacecraft. For instance, if spacecraft B conducts a CAM to avoid collision with spacecraft A, point (c) mandates that the CAM should not create another collision risk, this time with spacecraft C. Though the evidence supporting the explicit mention of point (c) is very important, and the proposal herein can accommodate considerations of secondary conjunctions, it is ultimately outside of the scope of this paper.⁸³

3. CUSTOMARY INTERNATIONAL LAW

Unification on the global scale is known as international custom.⁸⁴ When a policy becomes Customary International Law (CIL), it becomes binding on all states.⁸⁵ To reach CIL status, a strong national system must develop into a global practice.⁸⁶ If non-EU standards become the norm, then Union companies and government agencies would become dependent on outside systems. External dependence would curtail the sovereignty of the EU, leading to problematic situations regarding global competitiveness and national security.⁸⁷ This is especially deleterious with ROW rules, since there can only be one framework to be

⁸² European Commission (25 June 2025). *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex X, Point 5.2 at 35, COM(2025) 335 Final, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf. See Delmas, F., Nunes, P., Perez, C., (2024), Future Evolutions of EUSST Collision Avoidance Service, *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 11(1), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisse.2023.11.002> (The typical alert threshold is 5×10^{-4} . Reducing by one order of magnitude results in a PoC threshold of 5×10^{-5}).

⁸³ In this paper, certain terms are used interchangeably, such as “spacecraft” and “space asset,” and “HIE” and “conjunction.” Unless specified, the general meaning of terms is used, so “constellations” includes mega-constellations and giga-constellations, and “spacecraft” includes satellites and constellations. Additionally, the Commission conducted an impact assessment and selected “Policy Option 2+” as the preferred result: adopt a binding Union framework, paired with non-binding and support measures. In this paper, certain policies are only applicable under Policy Option 2+ (e.g. label mechanism). Overall, this paper is aligned with Policy Option 2+. See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), at 7, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

⁸⁴ National Space Society (6 May 2025). *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC_105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf at 2, (“[D]eveloping an STM system will avoid the risk of non-EU STM standards becoming the international norm, as this dependence would have a negative effect on European technological sovereignty”), (citing Giannopapa, C., & Antoni, N., (2023), *Space Traffic Management and its Dual Use: Space Security Strategies and Cooperation in Europe*, *Acta Astronautica*, 212, 41–47, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.01.038>).

⁸⁵ “Customary international law results from a general and consistent practice of states followed by them from a sense of legal obligation.” Restatement of the Law (Third), Foreign Relations of the United States, §102(2).

⁸⁶ National Space Society, (6 May 2025), at 4.

⁸⁷ Kolovos, A. (March 2024). Unravelling the EU’s Space Policy and Strategy: Impacts on Security and Defence Evolution, *London Institute of Space Policy and Law* (ISPL), at 4, (noting the war in Ukraine prompted the EU to identify space as a strategic domain for security and defence purposes).

effective.⁸⁸ Ultimately, effective laws are *clear* laws, and for Article 103(3) to gain the requisite clarity to become CIL, operators must understand how these factors are used in practice.⁸⁹

Regulatory hegemony is not new to the EU, as such an occurrence is documented and has been coined the “Brussels effect.”⁹⁰ To create a single market and achieve sovereignty on the global scale, the development of a STM system is a litmus test for the Union’s future wellbeing and stability.⁹¹

“In addition to being technically sound and efficient,” the objective of ROW rules is to integrate the matters of a larger space community.⁹² This balancing of interests is critical for the EU’s goal to remain sovereign because global adoption is dependent on stakeholder’s positive perception.⁹³

3.1. A Cohesive Structure

A standardised ROW framework would nonetheless be absolute if *different* rules are adopted.⁹⁴ Unlike driving on the road, where rules can change depending on the geographical boundary, orbital space lacks any regard for state boundaries.⁹⁵ Lacking a cohesive structure, different ROW instructions will inevitably interact with one another, potentially *increasing* the risk of collision.⁹⁶ “An STM regime followed only by one or a handful of nations would do little to create a safer space environment.”⁹⁷ Not only would this circumstance fail to create a safe orbital environment, but nations with more lenient rules would attract

⁸⁸ See *infra* section 3.1 A Cohesive Structure.

⁸⁹ Rule of Law Education Centre, *Characteristics of Effective Laws*, n.d., <https://www.ruleoflaw.org.au/education/civics-citizenship-and-laws/characteristics-of-effective-laws/>.

⁹⁰ Bradford, A. (2020). *The Brussels Effect: How the European Union Rules the World*, Oxford University Press. The Brussels Effect is “the phenomenon where the markets are transmitting the EU’s regulations to both market participants and regulators outside the EU.” This can happen by global corporations adjusting their conduct to be compatible with the EU market, then lobbying in their home states for adoption of EU regulations, to avoid the “flag of convenience” issue. This practice spreads EU regulations.

⁹¹ European Commission (15 February 2022). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report) at 2, JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004> (stating with regards to a global regulatory framework: “the EU must act now, swiftly, collectively and resolutely”).

⁹² Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 304, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

⁹³ Bertrand, R., Michel, M. (20–23 April 2021). *Assessment of Inter-Operator Rule-Based Collision Avoidance Operations* [Conference Presentation], Section 5: Conclusions and Future Work, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/> (“Acceptance and thus the wider adoption will be determined primarily by how fairly the rules are valued by the entities involved.”). See also International Telecommunication Union (ITU), (1992), *Constitution of the International Telecommunication Union*, (2023 ed., Art. 44, No. 196), (“any associated orbits . . . are limited natural resources and that they must be used rationally, efficiently, and economically”).

⁹⁴ National Space Society (6 May 2025). *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC_105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf at 2.

⁹⁵ See Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 313, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> (Orbit is multi-dimensional and governed by the “laws of astrodynamics,” making orbit “more geometrically complex.”).

⁹⁶ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 303, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> (Right-of-way rules “would let operators know what behaviour to expect from another operator even if they have not succeeded in establishing communication.”).

⁹⁷ National Space Society (6 May 2025), at 2.

greater demand.⁹⁸ Rather than permit counter-productive behaviour, proposed ROW rules should alleviate the risk of collision and incorporate the “complex web of interests” of the global space community.⁹⁹

In 2020, the European Space Policy Institute (ESPI) published a report on the EU’s need for a unified framework: *Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management* (2020 Report).¹⁰⁰ The 2020 Report followed the United States’ Space Policy Directive-3 (National Space Traffic Management Policy) in 2018, a presidential memorandum that provides guidelines to establish a U.S. approach to STM.¹⁰¹

By 2022, the EU published a joint communication to the European Parliament and Council: *An EU Approach for Space Traffic Management* (2022 Report).¹⁰² Therein, it identified four “drivers” of the EU STM initiative, one being the lack of international “rules of the road” for orbital actors.¹⁰³ As noted, given the unfettered nature of space, global alignment is critical.

In response to growing pressure, the EU proposed the *Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act) in 2025 as a regulatory compendium for the “development and function of an EU single market for the space sector.”¹⁰⁴ By unifying Member States’ space policies, access across twenty-seven Member States is opened, ultimately boosting the European economy.¹⁰⁵ Especially within the context of space, where space objects are used for education, military, communication, and weather purposes, protecting space assets is vital to the health of the Union.¹⁰⁶

⁹⁸ *Ibid.* Known as the “flags of convenience” problem, where states with lenient rules garner greater demand, thereby creating a system of actors that follow insufficient rules. *See supra* note 85.

⁹⁹ Frandsen, 2023, at 304. *See* Bertrand, R., Michel, M. (20–23 April 2021). *Assessment of Inter-Operator Rule-Based Collision Avoidance Operations* [Conference Presentation], Section 5: Conclusions and Future Work, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darnstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/>, (“Acceptance and thus wider adoption will be determined by how fairly the rules are valued by the entities involved.”); National Space Society, (6 May 2025), at 1, (“Internationally binding regulations regarding STM will only be achieved if States . . . expect a specific as well as collective benefit”).

¹⁰⁰ European Space Policy Institute (January 2020). *ESPI Report 71 – Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management – Full Report*.

¹⁰¹ *Ibid.* at 1; U.S. Office of the President (18 June 2018). *Space policy directive-3: National space traffic management policy*, The White House. At the time of the United States’ SPD-3 release, the EU did not have a comparable STM policy yet.

¹⁰² European Commission (15 February 2022). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report), JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004>.

¹⁰³ *Ibid.* at 3–4, (The other three “drivers” are (in order as mentioned): 1. “New Space” (referring to the economic change regarding space initiatives, specifically the low cost and high return relationship, encouraging more space actors); 2. rise of space traffic activity; and 3. threats to the security and resilience of space assets.)

¹⁰⁴ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Commission Staff Working Document, Executive Summary of the Impact Assessment Report* (Executive Summary), at 1, SWD(2025) 336 final. Note that the EU Space Act is still in negotiations.

¹⁰⁵ European Commission (2025). *Space Act*, at 9, (The Space Act is projected to make the EU space industry a EUR 700 billion market. Unifying rules across the EU creates a single market across twenty-seven States, streamlining access and reducing administrative hurdles).

¹⁰⁶ Mazurelle, F., Wouters, J., & Thiebaut, W. (2009). The Evolution of European Space Governance: Policy, Legal and Institutional Implications, *International Organizations Law Review*, 6(1), 155-190, at 189 (“One thing is clear: . . . space will be a true case study and a genuine test for European governance itself and for the future of the EU as a global actor.”). *See also* European Commission (10 March 2023). *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence* at 1, JOIN(2023) 9 final, Brussels, Belgium, (stating space is “critical” for strategic autonomy of the EU and its Member States).

4. ANALYSIS OF ARTICLE 103(3)(A)-(G)

4.1. Protection of Crew Vehicle

Rule: *In the event of conjunction, the crewed spacecraft has the right-of-way unless the other spacecraft is also crewed.*

The most important consideration is the safety of crewed vehicles during space activities. As established in the EU Space Act, the proposed CAMs by CASSPs must take “the utmost account of the protection of crewed vehicles.”¹⁰⁷ The protection of life is a moral and ethical principle that needs no explanation. In the context of international law, this concept is codified in treaties such as the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (1967) (Outer Space Treaty or OST), Article V, which regards astronauts as “envoys of mankind” whom shall receive “all possible assistance in the event of accident, distress, or emergency landing.”¹⁰⁸ Echoed in the *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (1967) (Rescue Agreement or ARRA), Article II, which requires a state to take “all possible steps to rescue [personnel] and render them all necessary assistance.”¹⁰⁹ Nearly all EU Member States have ratified the OST and ARRA,¹¹⁰ but regardless of ratification status, both treaties have become Customary International Law (CIL)¹¹¹ and therefore, are binding on all states.¹¹²

Principles regarding human safety are also reflected in aviation and maritime law.¹¹³ In the former, Article 25 of the Chicago Convention provides that states must provide “measures of assistance to aircraft in distress in its territory.”¹¹⁴ In the latter, Article 98 of UNCLOS specifies that only if “serious danger” would not be rendered onto the aiding ship, crew, or passengers, can a captain provide assistance to

¹⁰⁷ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 103(3), at 105, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁰⁸ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty), 27 January 1967, 610 U.N.T.S., Art. V, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/outerspacetreaty.html>.

¹⁰⁹ *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space* (Rescue Agreement), 3 November 1967, 610 U.N.T.S. 205, Art. II, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/rescueagreement.html>.

¹¹⁰ COPUOS, *Status of International Agreements relating to activities in outer space as at 1 January 2025*, (A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.9), https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_9_0.html/AC105_C2_2025_CRP09E.pdf (As of January 1, 2025, Luxembourg and Malta are signatories to the OST. Estonia has not ratified the Rescue Agreement. Latvia has not ratified the OST nor the Rescue Agreement).

¹¹¹ “Customary international law results from a general and consistent practice of states followed by them from a sense of legal obligation.” Restatement of the Law (Third), Foreign Relations of the United States, §102(2).

¹¹² *Ibid.*

¹¹³ See Convention on International Civil Aviation (Chicago Convention), (1948), Art. 25, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/unts/volume%2015/volume-15-ii-102-english.pdf>; United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), (1994), Art. 98, https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

¹¹⁴ Chicago Convention, (1948), Art. 25.

vessels in distress or to those in “danger of being lost.”¹¹⁵ Member States in the EU are parties to both Conventions and portions of each treaty are regarded as CIL.¹¹⁶

Crewed vehicles should always have the right-of-way (ROW). This rule is grounded in international law and the natural inclination to protect human life. If an actor in a conjunction event is equipped with the ability to manoeuvre and is not manned, it will give-way to the crewed vehicle. To illustrate, consider a hypothetical HIE between the International Space Station (ISS) and a manoeuvrable satellite: the ISS maintains course and the satellite performs a CAM.

An exception applies during the launch of a crewed spacecraft, where it must give-way to vehicles in orbit.¹¹⁷ It is impractical to place a global burden on operators to monitor crewed launches, accurately determine if orbital adjustments are needed, and implement such CAMs with zero margin of error. Furthermore, mandating crewed spacecraft to give-way to objects in-orbit reinforces the expectation on all launches and ensures consistency.¹¹⁸

4.2. State of the Spacecraft

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft that is unresponsive or in distress has the right-of-way.*

Spacecrafts are susceptible to countless vulnerabilities like geomagnetic storms, cyberattacks, and internal electrical issues.¹¹⁹ In the worst-case scenario, these impacts can render a spacecraft defunct, or in a slightly more optimistic situation, vessels can be rendered temporarily unresponsive or distressed.¹²⁰ Because this analysis is limited to two *manoeuvrable* spacecraft—per Article 103(1)—this paper will only address unresponsive and distressed vessels.

Referring to the Space Act itself, it is not clear whether the state of a spacecraft is meant to include the notion of being “unresponsive.” The state of a spacecraft is mentioned in Article 65(1), which articulates the “necessary data and information” that operators must provide to the EU Space Surveillance and

¹¹⁵ UNCLOS, (1994), Art. 98.

¹¹⁶ Congressional Research Service, (2023), *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS): Living Resources Provisions*, (CRS Report No. R47744), <https://www.congress.gov/crs-product/R47744#fn6> (noting that portions of UNCLOS are CIL); Curtis, Mallet-Prevost, Colt & Mosle LLP, (n.d.), *Public International Law UNCLOS*, Curtis.com, <https://www.curtis.com/glossary/public-international-law/unclos#:~:text=UNCLOS%20has%20been%20ratified%20by%20the%20United%20States%20of%20America>, (noting the EU Member States have ratified UNCLOS); Wouters, J., Verhoeven, S., *State Aircraft*, Max Planck Encyclopaedia of Public International Law, Oxford Public International Law, <https://opil.ouplaw.com/display/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e1223> (noting portions of the Chicago Convention are CIL); ICAO Member States, <https://www.icao.int/about-icao/member-states> (listing EU Member States as Contracting Parties to the International Civil Aviation Organization, a regulatory body established by the Chicago Convention).

¹¹⁷ See American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA), (24 October 2022), *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-2: Perform Launch Collision Avoidance (LCOLA) Against Crewed Space Assets, at 9 (stating collision avoidance analysis during launch has undisputed importance in protecting crewed vehicles).

¹¹⁸ See *infra* section 4.4 Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission.

¹¹⁹ *Hazards of Space: How Satellite Missions Can Go Wrong* (25 September 2018). Capital Technology University [Blog], <https://www.captachu.edu/blog/hazards-of-space-how-satellite-missions-can-go-wrong>.

¹²⁰ *Ibid.* During NASA’s Fermi mission, a satellite entered “safe mode” until an issue with a solar array was resolved; SSH Communications Security, *Satellite Cybersecurity: Threats & Impacts*, <https://www.ssh.com/academy/satellite-cybersecurity-threats-impacts#:~:text=Operational%20and%20Strategic%20Impacts%20of%20the%20disruption%20more%20damaging> (cyberattacks can cause communication loss between the spacecraft and operator).

Tracking (SST) Portal¹²¹ including: “positioning, *state* of the spacecraft, [and] possibility to communicate.”¹²² Because the terms “positioning” and “communicate” flank the term “state,” the meaning of “state” does not include positioning or communicating since it was stated separately.¹²³ With this in mind, “unresponsive” should generally refer to the operator’s inability to control the vessel.

If a spacecraft is unresponsive, the spacecraft should have the ROW.¹²⁴ This follows logically because an unresponsive spacecraft is uncontrollable and therefore unable to conduct CAMs. Similarly, COLREGS denotes a “vessel not under command” as lacking the ability to manoeuvre through “some exceptional circumstance.”¹²⁵ During a collision risk, vessels not under command are provided as a stand-on vessel, which is equivalent to having the ROW.¹²⁶

When a spacecraft is *temporarily* unresponsive, the spacecraft should still have the ROW. Rule 7(a) of COLREGS supports this, stating: “If there is any doubt, such risk shall be deemed to exist.”¹²⁷ Rule 7(a) mandates ships to err on the side of safety when there is a risk of collision. The same should apply to spacecraft.

A vessel in distress should receive the ROW. The reasoning is dual-purpose: (1) a distressed spacecraft may also be unresponsive, therefore lacking the ability to manoeuvre, and (2) if the distressed vessel is crewed, this rule adheres to the proposal in section 2.2 Protection of a Crewed Vehicle by giving the crewed spacecraft with the ROW. Like a distressed spacecraft, an aircraft completing an emergency landing is given the ROW against other aircraft.¹²⁸ In its rule statement, the ICAO references an important caveat: the status of the distressed vessel must be *known*.¹²⁹ Spacecraft operators should report status changes to the EU-SST, so others are informed. Like using the November-over-Charlie flag position to alert of a vessel in distress or the spoken word MAYDAY, notifying others through the use of distress signals is common practice, and similar reporting requirements should be imposed on operators.¹³⁰

4.3. *Eccentricity of the Spacecraft’s Orbits*

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the space object with the higher eccentricity value is responsible for conducting a collision avoidance manoeuvre, unless the eccentricity is required for the mission.*

The eccentricity of an orbit is defined as “[t]he amount of which the orbit around Earth deviates from a perfect circle.”¹³¹ A space object with a higher eccentricity means its trajectory uncertainty grows faster

¹²¹ EU Space Surveillance and Tracking (2025). *EU SST Expands its User Community and Sensors Network*, <https://www.eusst.eu/newsroom/news/eu-sst-expands-its-user-community-and-sensors-network> (Over 500 satellites globally are protected by EU-SST and over 200 organisations are receiving services from the EU-SST).

¹²² European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 65(1) at 81, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (emphasis added).

¹²³ The Law Dictionary.org, *Noscitur A Sociis*, <https://thelawdictionary.org/noscitur-a-sociis/> (This type of legal interpretation is known as *noscitur a sociis* (“it is known by the company it keeps”). “[I]t is the concept that the intended meaning of an ambiguous word depends on the context in which it is used”).

¹²⁴ This rule is subject to exploitation by actors who wish to have the ROW. Proper documentation requirements and investigations *inter alia* can limit the pervasiveness of unethical practices. See section 6 Proposals and Limitations.

¹²⁵ COLREGS Rule 3(f).

¹²⁶ COLREGS Rule 18(a)-(c).

¹²⁷ COLREGS Rule 7(a).

¹²⁸ ICAO Annex 2, 3.2.2.5.3.

¹²⁹ *Ibid.* (ground-aircraft must be “aware” of the other’s need to conduct an emergency landing to give way).

¹³⁰ COLREGS Annex IV(f); ICAO Annex 2, Appendix 1.1.

¹³¹ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 313, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>. See The European

with time, posing a higher risk to other space actors.¹³² Additionally, objects in eccentric orbits move fastest when closest to the Earth (perigee), and slowest when farthest away (apogee). At the perigee, eccentric objects have a higher velocity, which increases the risk of collision with other space actors.¹³³ Recognizing the risk of eccentric orbits in LEO, the French national space agency, *Centre National D'Etudes Spatiales* (CNES), required “the object with the greatest eccentricity shall manoeuvre.”¹³⁴ For this factor, the following rule applies: space objects with greater eccentricity must give way to space objects with lower eccentricity values.

While spacecrafts and constellations can experience slight eccentricity during normal operations in LEO,¹³⁵ most spacecraft in LEO have a nearly circular orbit ($e < 0.1$).¹³⁶ To preserve this environment and maintain safety, it follows to incentivize space actors to correct orbital deviations to preserve the non-eccentric orbit in LEO. Imposing an affirmative duty to correct these deviations will ensure orbital space is predictable for other actors. Furthermore, by having eccentric spacecraft give way to vessels with lower eccentricity, it can incentivize appropriate behaviour in orbit and proper planning for injection launches and transfer orbits.¹³⁷

An exception is created for a conjunction event with a spacecraft that requires eccentricity because of its mission. In such a scenario, it is unnecessary to incentivize operators to reduce eccentricity because the eccentricity is *required*, and the space object is more likely to be stationed in an eccentric orbit rather than LEO.¹³⁸ For example, a spacecraft launched for an interplanetary mission requires a greater eccentricity. Here, it is unlikely that the space object with the higher eccentricity will be able to conduct CAMs, especially at the perigee, and continue the operation of its mission. In such a situation, if a spacecraft needs eccentricity for its mission-type, CASSPs should continue the Article 103(3) analysis.

The Space Act Annex IV 1.4(c)(i) supports this exception by requiring CASSPs to adjust a spacecraft’s screening volume depending on the orbit regime. This acknowledges that different orbits have different collision risk levels and a spacecraft’s collision assessment should be receptive to these differences. Considering that most objects with eccentric orbits are positioned in the Highly Eccentric Orbit (HEO) or transfer orbits, Annex IV 1.4(c)(i) works naturally with this exception.

To apply this rule, eccentricity values need to be updated, reported, and shared amongst other actors via the EU-SST Portal.

Space Agency, *Types of Orbits*, https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Space_Transportation/Types_of_orbits (Perfectly circular orbits are denoted by the number zero, and highly eccentric orbits are closer to the number one.).

¹³² See generally (1998) Jack D. Fisher, *The Evolution of Highly Eccentric Orbits*, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA356381.pdf>.

¹³³ C.f. Braun, V., Brunetti, G., Campiti, G., Ciminelli, C., Di Sciascio, E. (July 2023). *Orbital Kinematics of Conjunctioning Objects in Low-Earth Orbit and Opportunities for Autonomous Observations*, *Acta Astronautica*, vol. 208, 355–366, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.04.032> (Less than 1% of conjunction events in LEO involve a highly eccentric space object that only transits the LEO region near its perigee.).

¹³⁴ Frandsen, 2023, at 314.

¹³⁵ Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G. (2023). *Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management*, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf (Eccentricity in LEO can be caused by conducting CAMs and the impact of atmospheric drag. A simulation of the Starlink constellation utilized *daily* manoeuvres to correct orbital deviations—mirroring the function of an autonomous system).

¹³⁶ Braun, V., Brunetti, G., Campiti, G., Ciminelli, C., Di Sciascio, E. (July 2023). (Objects in a conjunction event “usually share similar orbital shapes, as 87% of all orbits are nearly-circular ($e < 0.01$).”).

¹³⁷ The European Space Agency, *Types of Orbits*. Transfer orbits modify spacecraft eccentricities in preparation for moving into a different orbit. Injection launches identify the orbit a spacecraft will first launch into, before the spacecraft moves into the orbit for long-term needs.

¹³⁸ Eccentric orbits include transfer orbits and a Highly Eccentric Orbit (HEO).

4.4. Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft in an active launch phase, re-entry phase, or in active in-space operations and services has the right-of-way.*

Mission phases include the launch & early orbit phases (LEOP), orbit raising, in-orbit operations (ISOS), and disposal phases.¹³⁹ The type of mission most plausibly refers to a spacecraft's operational behaviour, as in *how* a spacecraft flies.

Spacecraft *preparing* for launch should give-way to spacecraft established in their orbit.¹⁴⁰ Yielding to traffic in-orbit has well-grounded reasoning, as the inverse would force orbiting operators to be aware of launches around the world. This rule also incentivizes operators to screen orbits based on conjunction risks and carefully select launch times.¹⁴¹ However, criticism suggests that yielding to traffic in-orbit can effectively bar new entrants.¹⁴² But as it stands, this criticism does not hold much ground in current policies, as evidenced in *NASA's Spacecraft Conjunction Assessment and Collision Avoidance Best Practices Handbook*, which requires the spacecraft "ascending/descending" to "yield the right-of-way to existing on-orbit assets."¹⁴³

Additionally, aviation law holds a similar mandate when dealing with amphibious aircraft. When seaplanes land on or take off from the water, the aircrafts are required, to the extent practicable, to avoid impeding the activity of vessels.¹⁴⁴

When a spacecraft is moving between orbits, it should also yield to those already established in the orbit. The American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) published a report that supports this

¹³⁹ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 76(4), COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁴⁰ See *Nonreimbursable Space Act Agreement Between The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and Space Exploration Technologies Corp (SpaceX) For Flight Safety Coordination with NASA Assets*, Point 2, at 3, https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/nasa-spacex_starlink_agreement_final.pdf (Point 2 addresses Starlink's responsibility to make "reasonable efforts" to use pre-launch analysis to reduce PoC in "early-orbit operations phase").

¹⁴¹ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (24 October 2022). *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-2: Perform Launch Collision Avoidance (LCOLA) Against Crewed Space Assets, at 9; United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs, (2021); *Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space*, at 14, (Registration requirements help States act in accordance with the OST Article VIII and the Registration Convention). See Cesari, L. (16 February 2024), *Developing an EU Space Law: The Process of Harmonising National Regulations*, *McGill Institute of Air & Space Law*, <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/article/developing-eu-space-law-process-harmonising-national-regulations> (Per Article 189 of TFEU, Member States in the EU have exclusive control over administrative and procedural aspects of national activities, including registration and liability).

¹⁴² Frandsen, H. O. (2023). *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 304, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042> ("the granting of right-of-way to satellites already in operation over newly launched satellites could potentially make it difficult for late-comers to enter specific crowded orbits").

¹⁴³ National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). *NASA Spacecraft Conjunction Assessment and Collision Avoidance Best Practices Handbook* (February 2023). 4.1: *Ascent to/Disposal from the Constellation's Operational Orbit*, at 15, ("The ascending/descending spacecraft that is equipped to maneuver needs to yield the right-of-way to existing on-orbit assets by performing risk mitigation maneuvers or ascent/descent trajectory alterations").

¹⁴⁴ ICAO Annex 2, 3.2.6.1.4.

reading: “Transiting spacecraft should assume the responsibility for performing mitigation actions to avoid other satellites that are in their main operational orbits.”¹⁴⁵

In situations where a spacecraft is actively launching, the ability of the spacecraft to conduct CAMs is significantly reduced due to the lack of manoeuvrability capacity when following a pre-planned trajectory. Similarly, a spacecraft will have limited manoeuvrability in active re-entry operations because of the Earth’s gravity or because of natural decay.¹⁴⁶ In both scenarios, the spacecraft will not have the capability to conduct CAMs and therefore, has the ROW. Like a spacecraft entering Earth’s orbit, a plane “landing or in the final stages of an approach to land” is given the ROW.¹⁴⁷

When preparing for disposal, operators must give-way to other actors to the best of their ability. Asset disposal, otherwise known as active debris removal (ADR), is a kind of ISOS.¹⁴⁸ Without ADR, space junk can accumulate in orbit,¹⁴⁹ leading to a congestion issue that constellations and New Space actors exacerbate.¹⁵⁰ During ISOS operations, the servicing spacecraft should generally have the ROW. This rule is subject to change based on the future frequency of ISOS and the risk of exploitation.¹⁵¹

When the servicer spacecraft is no longer *actively* servicing the client spacecraft or debris, it should give-way to others.¹⁵² To achieve its mission, ISOS must be equipped with manoeuvring capabilities. Therefore, to give such an equipped spacecraft the ROW, especially at the cost of others’ remaining fuel or GPS functions, would ultimately defeat the purpose of its mission: sustainability. Because the client spacecraft is maintaining its orbit, and to reduce additional interference, the ISOS spacecraft must give way. This spectrum, where an ISOS spacecraft has the ROW when operating on another but has to give way when otherwise orbiting, is meant to curtail unnecessary interference and reduce the likelihood of exploitation. To apply this rule, the understanding of *when* the ISOS operation has commenced and terminated will need to be identified.

4.5. Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft with the higher operational capacity for conducting a collision avoidance manoeuvre must conduct a collision avoidance manoeuvre.*

¹⁴⁵ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (24 October 2022). *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-1: Create and Expediently Publish Your Strategy to Transport Yourself to Your Final Orbit, at 8.

¹⁴⁶ Natural decay allows a satellite to passivate fuel reserves and remain in-orbit until the spacecraft’s eventual re-entry. Note natural decay and re-entry are permitted methods of removal under EU Space Act Annex V (3.3).

¹⁴⁷ ICAO Annex 2, 3.2.2.5.1.

¹⁴⁸ See generally Institute of Air & Space Law, McGill University (Montreal, Canada), Institute of Air & Space Law, Cologne University (Cologne, Germany), International Association for the Advancement of Space Safety (Noordwijk, the Netherlands), (27 January 2012), *Active Debris Removal—An Essential Mechanism for Ensuring the Safety and Sustainability of Outer Space: A Report of the International Interdisciplinary Congress on Space Debris Remediation and On-Orbit Satellite Servicing*, Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Scientific and Technical Subcommittee, Forty-Ninth Session, A/AC.105/C.1./2012/CRP.16, Vienna, Italy, (ADR’s use is to “clean” orbit by removing unwanted debris, most commonly by expediting an object’s re-entry into the Earth’s atmosphere).

¹⁴⁹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (June 2023). *UNOOSA and ESA Release Updated Infographics About Space Debris*, <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/informationfor/media/unoosa-and-esa-release-infographics-and-podcasts-about-space-debris.html> (Satellites in LEO will usually fall back to Earth in less than 25 years, but “[h]ad the dinosaurs launched a satellite into the furthest geostationary orbit, it would still be up there today”).

¹⁵⁰ For the EU Space Act’s proposed requirements on de-orbiting, see Article 70(3)(c) and Annex V (3.4.2).

¹⁵¹ This rule can be exploited by having routine ISOS or falsely claiming active ISOS operations to get the ROW. To curtail such exploitation, the parameters of *when* an ISOS operation is occurring can be narrowly defined.

¹⁵² EU Space Act Annex V (3.3)(f) (a spacecraft can be removed by ISOS operations).

The spacecraft with the higher operational capacity for CA manoeuvres must give way to the space object with the limited ability to manoeuvre.¹⁵³ Annex IV (2.1) of the Space Act supports this rule in requiring operators to perform CAMs when a spacecraft is manoeuvrable. Similarly, maritime law grants the right-of-way based on the manoeuvrability of vessels. For instance, when power-driven vessels encounter sailing vessels, the latter are designated as “stand-on” because they do not have propelling machinery, only the wind.¹⁵⁴ A second comparison is to CubeSats, which are “generally equipped with a limited capability to manoeuvre in orbit.”¹⁵⁵

The EU Space Act does not define what constitutes a spacecraft’s “operational capacity”, and supplementing technical definitions is a nuanced practice. For instance, consider whether fuel-efficient propulsion contributes to a higher or lower operational capacity: chemical propulsion provides powerful bursts that can quickly change a satellite’s velocity, whereas electric propulsion changes a constellation’s velocity over a cumulative effect of many small firings.¹⁵⁶ A chemical propulsion system may appear to be more efficient, but the opposite is true: electric propulsion systems have “a fuel efficiency of 10-12 times greater than a chemical thruster.”¹⁵⁷ With most constellations using electric propulsion,¹⁵⁸ mega- and giga-constellations can travel farther and for longer on a given amount of fuel.¹⁵⁹ Thus, if a conjunction event requires a CAM within twelve hours, which spacecraft has the higher operational capacity: the mega-constellation that can expend fuel with less impact to operations,¹⁶⁰ or the satellite that can enact the CAM within the provided time restraint?

As mentioned, maritime law’s Rule 18 of COLREGS specifies that the hierarchy of vessels is based on *manoeuvrability*.¹⁶¹ The rule provides seven types of circumstances (i.e. vessel engaged in fishing) or characteristics of the vessel (i.e. seaplane) in which a vessel’s manoeuvrability is ranked.¹⁶² For example, a powerboat is higher in the hierarchy than a seaplane, so the seaplane gives way.¹⁶³ COLREGS Rule 17(ii) illustrates that even if vessel A is to stand-on, if it becomes apparent that vessel B is not giving way, vessel A must take CA action.¹⁶⁴ This rule requires vessels to remain vigilant, especially around vessels that are larger and less manoeuvrable.

¹⁵³ Article 103(1) designates that the CASSP assists in conjunction with two manoeuvrable spacecraft. Therefore, the analysis herein does not consider one object lacking CAM capabilities altogether.

¹⁵⁴ COLREGS Rule 3; Rule 18.

¹⁵⁵ European Space Policy Institute (January 2020). *ESPI Report 71 – Towards a European Approach to Space Traffic Management – Full Report*, at 12.

¹⁵⁶ *Comprehensive Overview of Satellite Propulsion Systems* (24 February 2026). The Lee Co. <https://www.theleeco.com/insights/comprehensive-overview-of-satellite-propulsion-systems/>.

¹⁵⁷ NASA (26 December 2012). *Ion Thruster Sets World Record*, <https://www.nasa.gov/image-article/ion-thruster-sets-world-record/>.

¹⁵⁸ NASA (17 March 2024). *State-of-the-Art of Small Spacecraft Technology*, https://www.nasa.gov/smallsat-institute/sst-soa/in-space_propulsion/, “While xenon is generally a superior propellant, krypton-fed Hall thrusters will likely become more common in the future, especially for large constellations.”

¹⁵⁹ NASA, (26 December 2012), *Ion Thruster Sets World Record*, <https://www.nasa.gov/image-article/ion-thruster-sets-world-record/>.

¹⁶⁰ *Cf.* COLREGS Rule 8(b). Rule 8(b) requires CAMs to be “large enough to be readily apparent to another vessel.” If the thruster systems on mega- and giga-constellations are tiny firings over a comparatively longer period of time, will it be sufficiently apparent to other actors that the constellations are taking CA action?

¹⁶¹ COLREGS Rule 18. Note, COLREGS is not based on crewed status.

¹⁶² *Ibid.*

¹⁶³ Note the relation between the landing and lift-off of a seaplane and the launch and re-entry of a space object. Rule 18 of COLREGS mandates a seaplane to give-way to actors already in the water, like the rule mandating launching space objects should give way to objects in-orbit.

¹⁶⁴ COLREGS Rule 17(ii).

By adopting this framework into the postulated hypothetical above, the mega-constellation must give way to the satellite, but the satellite's operators must stay cautious. If it appears that the mega-constellation is unable to perform the manoeuvre, the satellite must take CA action.¹⁶⁵

For the hypothetical question to even manifest, both actors need to know what propulsion system the other is using. This can be accomplished through the shared access of operational capabilities in the EU-SST Portal. A critique of sharing operational capabilities in the EU-SST Portal is that it will incentivize propulsion systems with inferior capabilities.¹⁶⁶ Bad actors will incorporate cheaper propulsion systems to take advantage of the ROW. Ultimately, the need for operational data sharing is echoed in the AIAA's report, which calls onto operators to update their information when CAM functions are hindered. Therefore, when such information is updated and shared, other operators "will recognize that they will bear the mitigation responsibility for any conjunctions with your satellite."¹⁶⁷ In other words, operators must remain cautious, especially until additional clarity is provided with regards to the term "operational capacity."

4.6. *Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation*

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the smaller constellation is responsible for conducting a collision avoidance manoeuvre.*

In Article 103(3)(b), the phrase "spacecraft that *is part of* a constellation" is partially ambiguous. By referencing spacecraft that constitute the constellation, rather than referencing the constellation itself, this factor alludes to other phases of a spacecraft's life cycle, like launching.¹⁶⁸ During launches, a satellite is not connected to the constellation but rather just "part" of it. Aircraft formations support this interpretation, as their formations include "periods of transition when aircraft are manoeuvring."¹⁶⁹ Therefore, just as satellites comprise a constellation, aircrafts comprise flight formations.

During both the launch-planning and the launch and early orbit phases (LEOP), a constellation must give-way to objects in-orbit to the extent practicable.¹⁷⁰ This rule is consistent with the approach for other launching vehicles. Specifically, Annex VI 2.2(d)(i) in the Space Act supports this rule, which mandates operators of mega- and giga-constellations to prove a limited PoC when transferring from injection to final orbit.¹⁷¹ In other terms, this means a mega- or giga-constellation cannot move into a different orbit

¹⁶⁵ This notion of operators remaining vigilant when the other has the duty to conduct a CAM is supported by all proposed rules herein, especially in the following section: 4.6 Involvement of a Spacecraft That is Part of a Constellation. The purpose of drawing this comparison with maritime law is to "fill the gap" presented by the lack of clarity in determining what "operational capacity" refers to, as explored in the hypothetical.

¹⁶⁶ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 17, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2023042>.

¹⁶⁷ American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) (24 October 2022). *Satellite Orbital Safety Best Practices Guide*, Version 2.0, Practice B-1: Create and Expediently Publish Your Strategy to Transport Yourself to Your Final Orbit, at 8.

¹⁶⁸ For example, had this factor been shortened to "involvement of a constellation," launching satellites would not be included because the satellites aren't *attached* to the constellation. This interpretation is supported by Article 88(3) stating: "prior to launch, or in the case of *satellites part of a constellation*, prior to the launch of the first batch of satellites . . ." (emphasis added). Article 88(3) shows that when satellites "part of a constellation" are involved, it includes the full life cycle of satellites, not only when the satellites are attached to the constellation. EU Space Act, Article 88(3), pg. 95. The textual analysis utilized here is referred to as syntactic analysis and *expression unius* (negative implication).

¹⁶⁹ ICAO Annex 2 (3.1.8), at 3-2.

¹⁷⁰ See *supra* section 4.4 Phase and Type of the Respective Space Mission.

¹⁷¹ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex VI, Point 2.2(d), at 20, COM(2025) 335 Final,

without proving the plan has a low risk of collision. By requiring a launching plan, especially in the case of large constellations, operators must comply with registration practices, which is “a key factor in the safety and the long-term sustainability of space activities.”¹⁷²

Smaller constellations must conduct CAMs and give-way to larger constellations. This is most evident in point (66) of the EU Space Act Proposal, which states: “specific obligations should be imposed to constellations varying according to the *size* of a constellation.”¹⁷³ One example is the comparison starting with Article 73(2)(a)(iv), which mandates operators to take the expected number of CAMs during the lifetime of the mega- and giga-constellation into consideration when selecting an orbit.¹⁷⁴ Compare this to Article 69(1), which does not explicitly mandate that the number of CAMs be taken into consideration when selecting an orbit for spacecraft. Placing a higher burden on mega- and giga-constellations in selecting an orbit can disincentivize larger space objects from selecting LEO and thereby insulating smaller actors.

Additionally, a smaller constellation must give-way during a larger constellation’s ISOS.¹⁷⁵ During these services, the larger constellation might be unable to conduct CAMs, regardless of whether the constellation’s CAM system is manual or automated. In this case, the smaller object has to give way. It is important to monitor for actors who take advantage of this exception by routinely sourcing ISOS or improperly claiming ISOS services to avoid conducting CAMs.

To apply the rule, operators need to know the size of another’s spacecraft, which can be shared through the EU-SST Portal. Using the EU-SST Portal, the size of a constellation can be appraised, but additional thought is required in determining whether satellites of *comparable* size are nonetheless deemed “larger” or “smaller” than the other based on a strict interpretation of definitions.¹⁷⁶ When two equally sized constellations are in a conjunction event, the CASSP must continue the Article 103(3) analysis.

Larger constellations utilize autonomous CAM systems because the scale of a single constellation is too much for operators to manage on their own.¹⁷⁷ Though an automated CAM is a relatively new piece of technology, its premise – the ability to self-manage CAM – has been accepted at face-value.¹⁷⁸ The EU

https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf

¹⁷² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA) (2021). *Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space*, Guideline A.5: Enhance the Practice of Registering Space Objects, at 14. Registration requirements help States act in accordance with the OST Article VIII and the Registration Convention.

¹⁷³ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Point 66 at 24, (emphasis added).

¹⁷⁴ European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article 73(2)(a)(iv) at 85.

¹⁷⁵ See European Commission, (10 July 2024), *In Space Operations and Services – A Strategic Ability for the Future*, https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/space-operations-and-services-strategic-ability-future_en.

¹⁷⁶ See European Commission (2025). Space Act, Article V (Definitions).

¹⁷⁷ National Space Society (6 May 2025). *Space Traffic Management: Legal Challenges and Considerations*, [Conference Room Paper], Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee, Sixty-Fourth Session, A/AC.105/C.2/2025/CRP.23, Vienna, Italy, https://www.unoosa.org/res/oosadoc/data/documents/2025/aac_105c_22025crp/aac_105c_22025crp_23_0_html/AC_105_C2_2025_CRP23E.pdf, at 4.

¹⁷⁸ The analysis of intra-constellation collisions is not included in the scope of this paper because it has been widely accepted as effective and generally involves only one O/O, therefore it does not fall within Article 103(3). See Borowitz, M., Gregoire, A., Gunter, B., Hejduk, M., Newman, L., & Schweiger, G., (2023), Validation of a Simulation Environment for Future Space Traffic Management, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230010359/downloads/Validation_of_a_Simulation_Environment_for_Future_Space_Traffic_Management.pdf (“It is assumed that constellations are able to self-manage their own collision avoidance . . .”).

Space Act mandates these automated systems for CA in mega- and giga-constellations.¹⁷⁹ In a scenario where a satellite or constellation is in a conjunction event with a mega- or giga-constellation, the sharing of information and planned manoeuvres will be imperative.¹⁸⁰ This is because the constellation's automated CAM system will be planning a manoeuvre and will not be able to consider what the smaller constellation or satellite might do without the requisite transfer of information.

A similar incident can appear in a conjunction event with two constellations, both equipped with automated systems. Because neither system will know the other is preparing for a CAM, it can lead to catastrophic results. Potential remedies include constant manual oversight and a common, automated system.

4.7. Age of the Spacecraft

Rule: *In the event of a conjunction, the spacecraft that can conduct a collision avoidance manoeuvre and end-of-life operations must conduct a collision avoidance manoeuvre.*

Generally, comparing the ages of two spacecrafts is unnecessary.¹⁸¹ It is also outside the scope of this paper to consider “older” spacecraft that were built without thrusters, as this falls outside the parameters of Article 103(1).¹⁸² This factor bears relevance in considering end-of-life (EOL) operations.¹⁸³

As stated in the EU Space Act, operators must have an EOL mission disposal plan and, in the case of mission extension, a renewed EOL plan.¹⁸⁴ These requirements ensure that spacecrafts have the necessary propellant for EOL manoeuvres.¹⁸⁵ This oversight limits the likelihood of a spacecraft running low on propellant before or during the disposal phase.¹⁸⁶ Therefore, older spacecrafts can continue to conduct CAM manoeuvres, because – all else being equal – there is a sufficient amount of propellant to continue operations. If a spacecraft needs their remaining amount of propellant for EOL operations, and is

¹⁷⁹ While satellites can have automated CAM systems, the EU Space Act only explicitly mandates larger constellations to be equipped with these functions. See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Annexes to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Annexes to the Space Act) Annex VI, Point 1.2(a) at 20, COM(2025) 335 Final,

https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2257596a-0485-465a-8031-a5d43eb5190f_en?file_name=Annexes-to-the-proposal-for-a-Regulation.pdf.

¹⁸⁰ European Space Agency (22 October 2019). *Automating Collision Avoidance*, Space Safety, https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/Automating_collision_avoidance.

¹⁸¹ For instance, a spacecraft in orbit for two weeks does not have “seniority” over a spacecraft in orbit for eleven days. Forgoing the “seniority” system can benefit later entrants by not asymmetrically imposing the burden to manoeuvre.

¹⁸² See Tech Briefs (1 January 2021). *Water-Powered Engines Offer Satellite Mobility*, <https://www.techbriefs.com/component/content/article/38352-water-powered-engines-offer-satellite-mobility#:~:text=At%20the%20time%2C%20CubeSats%20didn't%20have%20propulsion,about%20allowing%20pressurized%20propulsion%20systems%20onboard%20launches> (Previously, “CubeSats didn’t have propulsion systems”).

¹⁸³ EOL is defined as the “instant when a spacecraft or a launch vehicles orbital stage is permanently turned off, nominally as it completes its disposal phase, re-enters the Earth’s atmosphere, or can no longer be controlled by a space operator.” Removing space objects at EOL avoids contributing to the proliferation of space debris and is necessary for the sustainability of space orbits. See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 5, point 42 at 42, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335>.

¹⁸⁴ See generally European Commission (2025). *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex II.

¹⁸⁵ See European Commission (2025). *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex V (3.1.5)(a).

¹⁸⁶ See *supra* note 34 (The Liability Convention incentivizes States to monitor spacecraft registrations, mission extensions, and mandate EOL plans to prove there is sufficient propellant to conduct disposal manoeuvres.) See also *supra* section 4.5 Operational Capacity for Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres (discussing the EU Space Act’s requirement for orbit-selection plans and operators put on “notice”).

therefore unable to conduct a CAM and the EOL operation, the CASSP should propose a CAM that complies with the removal methods provided in EU Space Act Annex V (3.3) (a-f):

- a) Performing a controlled re-entry with a well-defined impact footprint on the surface of the Earth, to limit the casualty risk;
- b) Performing a semi-controlled re-entry after the end of the mission, in case the design complies with the casualty risk;
- c) Performing an immediate uncontrolled re-entry after the end of the mission, in case the design complies with the casualty risk;
- d) Allowing its orbit to decay naturally, in accordance with the limit of cumulative accidental collision probability, maximum orbital lifetime, and the limit for casualty risk;
- e) In exceptionally justified cases, for Very High LEO, disposal can take place in an orbit not interfering with protected regions and valuable orbits;
- f) Removal by ISOS.¹⁸⁷

When assessing the means in (a-f), factors like the Union Space Safety Labels and “design for demise” parameters will incentivize operators to engage in more responsible EOL operations.¹⁸⁸ Lastly, mission extension applications that have been rejected should be reported in the EU-SST and considered by the CASSP when delineating ROW responsibilities.¹⁸⁹

5. RIGHT-OF-WAY (ROW) DECISION MATRIX

The Decision Matrix is a visual aid that combines the rule statements for each Article 103(3) factor. The Decision Matrix is purposed for a CASSP’s use when deciding a manoeuvre strategy between two operators in a HIE.

¹⁸⁷ European Commission, (2025), *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex V (3.3)(a-f). Note that these means only apply to spacecraft in LEO. The spacecraft with limited propellant—for one reason or another—may be required to conduct a CAM, resulting in a loss of propellant. In such a scenario, this spacecraft will still be compliant with removal regulations given (f): “Removal by ISOS.”

¹⁸⁸ The Union Space Safety Labels will encourage adherence to high standards in safe sustainability (like an “eco-label”). See European Commission, (25 June 2025), *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 112 at 112, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (“Award and use of a Union Space Label”); European Commission, (15 February 2022), *Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council* (EU STM Report) at 11, JOIN(2022) 4 final, Strasbourg, France, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52022JC0004>. Factors like company branding or public opinion can also incentivize operators to engage in sustainable removal practices. See also EU Space Act, Annex V (3.5.1) (“For spacecraft being disposed . . . Union spacecraft operators shall consider *design for demise* as one of the steps to minimise the casualty risk.”) (emphasis added).

¹⁸⁹ A spacecraft with a rejected mission extension is still eligible for several removal means in the EU Space Act, Annex V, (3.3) (a-f). For operators to be aware of the spacecraft’s true status, the acceptance or denial of mission extensions should be published, enabling them to meaningfully participate in negotiations. European Commission, (2025), *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex V, (3.3) (a-f).

6. PROPOSALS AND LIMITATIONS

This paper concludes that Article 103(3) does not support a sequential hierarchy. The seven factors, however, can be rearranged to support an implied sequential hierarchy.

The following illustration provides a side-by-side look at the order of the factors within Article 103(3)(a)-(g) and the hierarchy proposed herein. The order of the factors under “PROPOSAL” is aligned with the Decision Matrix. The illustration gives a visual aid to better understand the differences between the two sequential orders. Each factor is given a respective colour to juxtapose the differences.

6.1. Comparative Illustration: Article 103(3) vs. Proposal

ARTICLE 103(3)	PROPOSAL
(a) Protection of crew vehicle	(a) Protection of crew vehicle
(b) Involvement of a spacecraft that is part of a constellation	(b) The state of the spacecraft
(c) The operational capacity for CA manoeuvres	(c) The eccentricity of the spacecraft’s orbits
(d) The state of the spacecraft	(d) The phase and type of the respective space mission
(e) The eccentricity of the spacecraft’s orbits	(e) The operational capacity for CA manoeuvres
(f) The age of the spacecraft	(f) Involvement of a spacecraft that is part of a constellation
(g) The phase and type of the respective space mission	(g) The age of the spacecraft

6.2. Proposals

The European Commission should provide greater clarity on the interpretation of Article 103(3) and relevant considerations within each factor, specifically with regard to the existence of an implied hierarchy. The sequential hierarchy is shown in the Decision Matrix above, but providing CASSPs with more resources would define the scope of each factor so that decisions are made with consistency and finality. Maritime and aviation analogies provide a helpful framework, but the applicability is limited given the inherent differences in the respective environments.

The ESA’s Space Safety Programme created the Collision Risk Estimation and Automated Mitigation (CREAM) project. CREAM is an automated risk assessment and manoeuvre-planning tool. It can be used to generate manoeuvre plans and support the decision-making process, facilitate negotiation between operators, and, in cases of disagreement with a proposed strategy, “refer the issue to a mediation service.”¹⁹⁰ The ESA stated: “The problem with establishing any kind of ‘rules of the road’ depends not only on the need to find consensus on such rules, but also on the availability of the technologies to make them a reality.”¹⁹¹

CREAM can be revolutionary in the STM field; however, if the EU looks to gain global dependence on Article 103(3) standards, automated technology must take these elements into consideration. Otherwise, if

¹⁹⁰ European Space Agency (12 August 2025). *CREAM: Avoiding Collisions in Space Through Automation*, https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Space_Debris/CREAM_avoiding_collisions_in_space_through_automation.

¹⁹¹ *Ibid.*

CREAM conflicts with Article 103(3) standards, it will lead to confusion among operators and CASSPs and poison the effectiveness of creating CIL.

Fostering the use of the EU-SST Portal will be imperative to achieving EU sovereignty and the implementation of ROW rules. In dealing with conjunction events, the most recent and factual understanding of the orbital environment must be provided to CASSPs. The EU-SST Portal should ensure users are reporting information with bearings on Article 103(3) analysis, such as: crewed status, automated CAM capabilities, unresponsive vehicles, mission extensions, manoeuvrability capabilities, etc.¹⁹² This paper, along with the applicability of the EU Space Act, did not include military or government assets.

Requiring CASSPs to document their decision-making process will reduce the likelihood of exploitation and help gather understandings of best practice.¹⁹³ The implementation of ROW rules might be subject to exploitation or inefficiency, especially with new technology such as ISOS and automated CAM. An audit system can expose these deficiencies.¹⁹⁴ On the operator level, Article 91(1) of the EU Space Act requires an “incident management process” for incident detection and reporting. As Member States integrate Article 91(1) in their domestic systems, Member States should be transparent with one another in their practices and discovery.

To achieve regulatory hegemony within the EU and ultimately, global sovereignty, the EU should continue working with non-EU partners and entities of the United Nations, like COPUOUS, for the adoption of a ROW framework. The EU can decide what behaviours to incentivize among space participants in allocating ROW benefits. With UN support, this framework can grow beyond the EU into global adoption. The clarity and functionality of ROW rules will be critical for global support.

Operators and CASSPs should be responsible for maintaining a record of their methodology in determining a manoeuvre strategy for each CAM. This would enable post-manoeuve accountability. Having a record of one’s decision-making process can enable an auditing agency to review the documentation for any errors or insights into “grey areas” of the policy. This recommendation should be limited in practice, as flooding operators and CASSPs with administrative forms will be too high of a burden.

6.3. *Limitations*

The strongest limitation on formulating a ROW framework and supporting its adoption on a global scale is the availability of Space Situational Awareness (SSA) data.¹⁹⁵ The foundation of regulating who gets to maintain the ROW and who must conduct a CAM is knowing where objects are in space. Without this knowledge, operators and CASSPs would rely on data that is false or incomplete. This can cause false positives for HIE alerts, or a complete lack of alerting, especially when certain data is regarded as “proprietary.” By accurately tracking space objects and maintaining the EU-SST Portal, a ROW framework can be put to the test.

The relevant technical implications of the proposed Article 103(3) hierarchy undoubtedly go beyond the scope of this paper. While this paper tries to incorporate practical considerations, such as eccentricity required for mission-type, there are mechanical limits of space travel that cannot be adjusted to policy. The proposed Article 103(3) hierarchy attempts to strike this balance between hopeful policy and realistic

¹⁹² See European Commission (2025). *Annexes to the Space Act*, Annex IV (2.4) at 10; European Commission, (2025), *Space Act*, Article 64 at 81.

¹⁹³ See European Commission (2025). *Space Act, Reporting of Significant Incidents*, Article 63 at 97.

¹⁹⁴ See European Commission (2025). *Space Act*, Article 94 at 99, (establishing the Union Space Resilience Network (EUSRN) for “support coordination and exchanges between the Agency and the competent authorities”); *Ibid.* at Article 102 (a “competent authority” can seek annual reports or compliance with specific investigations).

¹⁹⁵ See *supra* note 63.

technology, but feedback from the space community is warranted to determine the actual practicality of this ROW framework.

Within the space law community, there have been arguments against the urgency in creating a STM system, based upon a finding that the Earth's orbit is not crowded. To put such an argument in black-and-white, these contentions reject the Kessler Syndrome thesis.¹⁹⁶ To address this argument is outside the scope of this paper, as formulating ROW rules is independent of orbital congestion. Whether the Kessler Syndrome realizes is a separate inquiry.

7. CONCLUSION

A clear understanding of the rules is critical to orbital safety, so that each operator behaves in accordance with the rules and trusts that the *other* actor knows the rules and will also comply.¹⁹⁷ The factors considered in this paper are not exhaustive, as Article 103(3) makes clear,¹⁹⁸ but the analysis provides a starting framework for a ROW structure. Additionally, when evaluating these factors, impacts on neighbouring specialties like cybersecurity and satellite tracking services are noted.

This mutual confidence underpins the effectiveness of any ROW regime and strengthens the likelihood of its emergence as customary international law (CIL). As Hjalte Osborn Frandsen notes, “Any decision about right-of-way in orbit is therefore also a decision about who should bear the cost of manoeuvring.”¹⁹⁹ Article 103(3) of the EU Space Act represents a foundational opportunity to address this question precisely by establishing the world's first operational ROW framework for space.

If implemented, these provisions could harmonise EU Member States under a shared framework that preserves EU sovereignty. By adopting relevant policies seen in maritime and aviation law, the EU can set a precedent for global space-traffic governance, promoting safety, accountability, and international cooperation.

Future progress depends on transdisciplinary collaboration to critically appraise both the technical and regulatory feasibility of such a regime. Though the EU Space Act remains in the Commission for negotiations, its implementation by 2030 would mark a decisive step toward an enforceable, interoperable system of orbital conduct.

¹⁹⁶ Bhakare, N. (20–23 April 2021). *The Need for Evolving Legal Framework for Regulation of Space Debris Caused by Satellite Constellations* [Conference Presentation], Section 3: Kessler Syndrome and Space Debris, Eighth European Conference on Space Debris, Darmstadt, Germany (virtual), <https://conference.sdo.esoc.esa.int/> (Kessler Syndrome: In 1978, Kessler and Cour-Palais published their theory that “the more debris there is in orbit, the more collisions will occur,” thereby setting off a chain reaction. They predicted a “slow yet continuous growth in collision fragments that will not stop until the intact population is reduced in number”).

¹⁹⁷ Frandsen, H. O. (2021, Oct. 25-29). *Agreeing on the Rules-of-the-Road* [Conference article], at 2, 72nd International Astronautical Congress, Dubai, United Arab Emirates, <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3976854>.

¹⁹⁸ European Commission (25 June 2025). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Safety, Resilience and Sustainability of Space Activities in the Union* (Space Act), Article 103(3) at 105, COM(2025) 335 Final, 2025/0335 (COD), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0335> (“based on *at least* the following elements”) (emphasis added).

¹⁹⁹ Frandsen, H. O. (2023). *Towards Right-of-Way Rules in Orbit: Principles & Parameters for Sustainable Space Traffic*, *Air & Space Law*, vol 48(3), 297-318, at 303, <https://doi.org/10.54648/ajla2023042>.